

GenAI Chatbots for Knowledge Work: A Help or a Hindrance?

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Abstract—Generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) is rapidly evolving and becoming ubiquitous in many areas of our life. In particular, many workplaces have now adopted this technology to assist in and expedite their knowledge workers’ day-to-day labors. As this technology continues to evolve and takes its place alongside humans as a fundamental piece of our global cognitive architecture, it would be appropriate for us to understand its effects on human cognition so that we can implement policies, procedures, and guardrails that facilitate its effective adoption and mitigate any negative impacts it might have. I provide findings on the cognitive effects of GenAI chatbot use, identify factors which determine its efficacy, and provide practical policy suggestions which can increase efficacy and decrease negative cognitive impacts in the workplace.

Index Terms—Generative AI (GenAI), distributed cognition, digital cognitive offloading, extended mind, technostress

I. INTRODUCTION

GenAI systems predict content like code, images, and text leveraging multimodal models, large language models (LLMs), vision models, and other programmatic tools. In the last few years, GenAI has gone from futuristic research to production tools which are deeply embedded in day-to-day processes. Compared to other significant advancements which have had a profound impact on human cognition, like the internet and web search, GenAI is being adopted at a much more rapid rate [14]. For example, in 2023, Microsoft released Microsoft 365 Copilot which integrates GenAI with the Microsoft suite including Word, Excel, and Powerpoint [16]—applications which are essentially ubiquitous in knowledge work. Jaffe et. al found significant productivity gains when workers leveraged this tool with individuals reading 11% fewer emails and editing 10% more documents [15]. When tasks align with the model’s strengths, results are even more profound [1]. However, the cognitive consequences of integrating these tools into daily knowledge work remain unclear.

This paper seeks to understand how the daily use of Generative AI (GenAI) chatbots by knowledge workers for the completion of workplace tasks affects attention and problem solving.

A longstanding tradition in cognitive science frames humans as “cognitive misers,” a term coined by Fiske et. al in 1984 [17], which suggests that humans avoid effortful analytic thought when an easier option is available [18]. As shown by Barr *et al.*, heavy internet smartphone users scored lower on reasoning tests because they “allow their Smartphones

to do their thinking for them” [9]. From the perspective of distributed cognition and the extended mind, humans are “biotechnological hybrid(s)” which leverage external media as representations which are integral to cognition [6], [19]. From this perspective, GenAI is the latest adaptation to our evolving cognitive architecture. As our cognitive architecture adapts, understanding the impact of GenAI use on problem solving and attention in the workplace will help us effectively integrate it.

II. REVIEW DESIGN

A review of the literature was conducted to understand the effects on problem solving and attention of Generative AI use on day-to-day employee tasks. Literature was selected with the assistance of OpenAI’s GPT o3 with an emphasis on landmark studies and a mixture of experiments, reviews, and speculative articles. The literature collection includes industry studies as well as academic research. An emphasis was placed on recent work within the last 5 years with certain other studies making an appearance based on clout or relevance. Articles identified by GPT o3 were given an initial review for a reasonable number of citations in the literature, whether they appeared to be pertinent, and whether the collection of literature as a whole was strongly biased in one way. The collection of articles included here passed these subjective criteria and I subsequently added others which support them.

As I conducted the review, it became apparent that focusing on my original research question regarding “employee tasks” was too broad, including anything from authoring an email to digging a ditch in the hot Arizona sun. As such, I refined my scope to “knowledge work tasks” as the area of interest for this review.

It also became clear that there are not many research articles that explicitly study the effects of GenAI use on attention and problem solving when used daily in knowledge-work tasks. As such, articles explore other technologies that are similar in ubiquity and potential for cognitive offload, such as smartphones. In a similar vein, the effects of GenAI use in other domains are explored and synthesized as they apply to knowledge work.

Of the 15 original sources, 14 were retained. I do not include quotations or results from Nijssen *et al.* as this research ended up not fitting well with the rest of the synthesis. However, seven additional sources were added after the initial research collection phase which helped support key ideas.

III. RESULTS

I identified several main themes as integral to understanding how the daily use of GenAI chatbots by knowledge workers to complete workplace tasks affects attention and problem solving. These themes are as follows. Cognitive Offloading and the Extended Mind, Attention and Distraction, Problem-solving Efficacy and Task Fit, and Metacognition and Over-reliance.

A. Cognitive Offloading and the Extended Mind

Cognitive offloading, or the practice of leveraging tools and external representations in handling mental tasks, is foundational to understanding the potential impacts of GenAI use on cognition. GenAI chatbots offer this capability at a scale previously unseen, particularly in their application to knowledge work. Yet other technological frameworks like the internet, smartphones, and web searches might serve as an analogy useful for understanding the potential effects of extending our minds with digital devices. Andy Clark suggests that "humans are and always have been...extended minds" that "fluidly incorporate non-biological resources" [6]. From this extended mind perspective, the act of a knowledge worker offloading cognition to GenAI chatbots integrates these systems into their hybrid cognitive ecosystem.

Landmark research shows that humans are "cognitive misers" that readily offload complex reasoning where possible [20]. Across three studies, Barr *et al.* discovered a pattern of cognitive miserliness showing that "those who think more intuitively and less analytically" were more likely to offload cognitive tasks to their smartphones. They also showed that those who use their smartphones more, scored lower on reasoning tests [9].

Being a cognitive miser can have its benefits, though, as Grinschgl *et al.* demonstrated in a study on cognitive offloading and secondary task performance. They showed that the necessity to engage in multitasking leads to increased cognitive offloading, which in turn corresponds to more accurate performance on a secondary task [8]. This is of dual benefit in knowledge work—increased accuracy on tasks and freed cognitive capacity as a result of offloading which can be used elsewhere. However, in a mixed-method approach, Michael Gerlich found a "significant negative correlation between frequent AI tool usage and critical thinking abilities, mediated by increased cognitive offloading" and theorizes that cognitive offloading with AI tools may reduce cognitive engagement in critical thinking and problem-solving [4]. León-Domínguez also theorizes that high use of AI chatbots could impair functions like problem-solving, especially "if individuals do not utilize the freed cognitive resources for other tasks that pose cognitive challenges" [5]. While cognitive offloading with Generative AI chatbots may benefit task accuracy and free cognitive capacity in knowledge workers, it may also negatively impact critical thinking skills, attention, and problem-solving capacity.

Critically, the impact on cognition could be moderated by whether or not knowledge workers effectively leverage

cognitive offloading and use freed mental resources to engage in other cognitively challenging tasks. This could be the difference between a functional shift of cognitive load to GenAI tools and away from human minds and a true extended mind where a human and GenAI chatbot work together as an integrated cognitive system.

B. Attention and Distraction

As touched on in the previous section, leveraging generative AI chatbots for knowledge work has the potential to significantly affect attention. Depending on the type of task and how the chatbot is used to offload cognitive tasks, it can either positively affect attention by freeing cognitive resources and focus for other tasks or it can degrade attention by increasing multitasking behavior.

Hasan *et al.* report that "frequent digital multitasking is associated with decreased cognitive control and greater distractibility" [11] and is corroborated by Ophir *et al.* who found that "heavy media multitaskers are more susceptible to interference from irrelevant environmental stimuli and from irrelevant representations in memory" [10]. Frequent context switching could be to blame for this effect where toggling between tasks and modes of executing tasks could induce cognitive strain and decrease attention control on any one task.

However, well-designed GenAI chatbots can increase attention by freeing mental resources through cognitive offloading. In Grinschgl *et al.*, for example, the effects of a two-second lockout on the model window was enough to completely eradicate the benefit of cognitive offloading [8], highlighting the necessity of considering latency in chatbot design.

Further, allocating the proper tasks to GenAI chatbots can also increase attention as hinted by Jaffe *et al.* where Microsoft Copilot users read 11% fewer emails and spent 4% less time interacting with them and were able engage in more complex tasks, editing 10% more documents overall [15]. This research indicates that offloading more mundane knowledge-work tasks to GenAI chatbots may increase free attention for more cognitively complex tasks.

To summarize, when considering the effects of GenAI chatbot use on attention, whether the user engages in frequent multitasking, the chatbot's design and latency, and the type of tasks offloaded are all key to determining the polarity of the effects.

C. Problem-solving Efficacy and Task Fit

In the same stride as attention, it is important to understand the effects of GenAI chatbot use on problem-solving efficacy, or the quality and efficiency at which knowledge-work tasks are completed.

Research shows significant improvements in problem-solving efficacy when the task fits the technology. In a landmark article, Dell'Acqua *et al.* proposed the concept of a "jagged technological frontier." They indicate that when the task fits within the set of tasks which GenAI performs well on, the results of GenAI assistance is profound. They found that consultants performing tasks with GPT-4 assistance completed

12.2% more tasks on average at a 25.1% quicker rate and with 40% higher quality as compared to those without GPT-4 assistance. However, the research was quick to point out that when tasks did not fit within the "jagged frontier," consultants with GenAI assistance performed significantly worse than their peers without assistance—a full 19% less likely to produce a correct solution [1]. This highlights the importance of AI literacy among knowledge workers where AI-task fit can be effectively assessed rather than blindly relying on GenAI.

Urban *et al.* offers further evidence of enhanced problem-solving capacity by reporting that university students that leveraged ChatGPT for complex creative problem-solving tasks had significantly higher self-efficacy for task resolution as well as enhanced quality, elaboration, and originality of solutions over peers without ChatGPT [2]. This aligns with the idea that GenAI may handle the more tedious aspects of knowledge work effectively while freeing human cognitive capacity for deeper ideation.

Short-term benefits to problem-solving are not the full story, however. Long-term effects are not well studied, but some researchers believe that deskilling and monotonization of ideas are a possible effect of GenAI use in knowledge work over time. For example, Dell'Acqua *et al.* found that in consultants with AI "there is a marked reduction in the variability of ideas compared to those not using AI" [1]. This sentiment is echoed by Singh *et al.* as they highlight that GenAI may promote "passive consumption of potentially one-sided views...limiting exposure to diverse perspectives" [14].

While potential short-term effects on problem-solving efficacy are profound when the AI-task fit is right, the possible implications on long-term effects on human problem-solving capacity highlight the importance of intentional use and thoughtful involvement of the human user in the cognitive system.

D. Metacognition and Over-reliance

While GenAI can clearly be a cognitive aid, there is some concern that it could also short-circuit reflective thinking. That is, if AI always results in quick responses a cognitive miser may become overly reliant on it, skipping important steps of understanding problems, evaluating solutions, and learning through effort. These shortcomings could have negative long-term effects problem-solving and attention capacities.

Singh *et al.* refer to this over-reliance as "metacognitive laziness." They propose that the ease of GenAI use for complex tasks "may bypass important cognitive processes that typically occur during slower, deliberate learning" and that "over-reliance on GenAI can reduce...cognitive difficulty, which can reduce the activation of deeper metacognitive processes necessary for analytical reasoning" [14]. In knowledge work, this kind of metacognitive passivity could lead to decreased attention and patience, reduced learning, and poor accuracy on tasks due to blind trust. Indeed, a survey of knowledge workers suggests that greater confidence in GenAI is linked to reduced critical thinking [14]. Other research has found that heightened perceived usefulness of GenAI and decreased

perceived difficulty of a task is correlated with over-confidence in GenAI performance [2] which could further lead to blind trust in a spiral effect.

These sources highlight the importance of deliberate actions to safeguard metacognitive function and reduce over-reliance. The literature contains many suggestions whereby we might do so. In a paper exploring GenAI in education, Michael Gerlich echos the concern of blind trust and proposes mitigation through intentional cognitive engagement and suggests that educators "promote critical thinking, problem-solving, and independent learning" [4]. Andy Clark suggests a trust-but-reflect approach when he states that "learning how to both trust and question our best AI-based resources in this way is one of the most important skills that our evolving educational systems will now need to install" [6]. Research done by Suriano *et al.* ties together Clark and Gerlich emphasizing Gerlich's point about actively promoting engagement and knowledge. They found that AI chatbot use in education can positively affect critical thinking skills when use is accompanied by a positive attitude and trust which they found to be indicators of engagement [12]. Proposed by Singh *et al.*, metacognitive prompting is another suggested mitigation in which an AI system encourages the user to consider alternative perspectives, assess their comprehension, or explore biases, and limitations of AI responses via directed questions [14].

In sum, GenAI use in the workplace could have long-term impacts on problem solving and attention. However, there are techniques which appear to keep the user metacognitively engaged, which could mitigate these effects.

E. Discussion

1) *Moderating Factors:* Three key moderators are apparent in the literature: Literacy, tool design, and usage style.

Literacy encompasses both AI literacy, which is an understanding of AI, how it works, and what it is good at, as well as task-domain literacy, which is knowledge of the underpinnings of the task at hand. A quasi-experimental study exploring the use of ChatGPT in education found that both types of literacy were significant indicators of the effective use of AI to solve knowledge work problems [3]. The "jagged frontier" supports the necessity of AI literacy proposing that when task-AI fit is right, productivity gains are profound [1]. This highlights the importance of fostering AI and task-domain literacy. Further, as seen in D. Metacognition and Over-reliance and C. Problem-solving and Efficacy of Task Fit, GenAI use can actually contribute to metacognitive laziness and degrade problem-solving capacity over time. Speculatively, these pose risk to task-domain literacy through deskilling. Over-reliance and over-trust without cognitive involvement by the human may also pose a risk to AI literacy.

As seen in the study by Grinschgl *et al.* referred to in B. Attention and Distraction, tool design is paramount to effective use of GenAI where subjectively minor issues with interface design can wipe out any benefit of AI tools to multitasking—a fundamental part of knowledge work where many workers operate on multiple tasks simultaneously (like responding to

a high priority email in the middle of a programming task). This study found that a simple 2 second lockout on the tool reduced the benefit to zero. This highlights the importance of intentional interface design with low latency and streamlined workflows.

AI usage style can be seen as a spectrum where one end is no use at all and the other end is offloading every task to the AI chatbot with blind trust, never taking an active part in the cognitive process. It is clear that some balance is required. In a study of employees, Chuang *et al.* found that those who felt efficient and capable with AI experience less stress, more engagement, and higher job satisfaction, whereas those who did not feel efficient and capable experienced increased technostress, negatively impacting job satisfaction and work-family conflict [13]—pointing out the importance of enabling employees in their use of GenAI tools.

2) *Practical Recommendations:* Based on the given moderators, there are practical steps which companies, teams, and individuals can take to support knowledge workers in the effective use of GenAI chatbots. These steps will help improve problem-solving and attention while mitigating the potential downsides of AI use.

Frequent and engaging trainings for knowledge workers on AI-user best practices should be implemented. Trainings should emphasize what GenAI is good at and what it is not—highlighting when possible the “jagged frontier” so that the user is enabled to avoid accuracy pitfalls due to task-AI mismatch. They should also inform the knowledge worker about the risks presented in this research so that they are encouraged to monitor their own cognitive involvement and attention in solving problems such that they can implement individual protocols for self-monitoring metacognitive engagement. Finally, trainings should teach the AI user how to effectively leverage the interface of the tools at their disposal specific. This will raise self-efficacy, leading to reduced technostress.

While frequent and engaging AI trainings can encourage knowledge workers to adopt a trust-but-reflect, human-in-the-cognitive-loop, usage style, as we have seen previously, people are cognitive misers, so promoting development of features which actively encourage and improve critical thinking and problem solving through metacognitive prompting is paramount to mitigating potential negative effects of GenAI use on metacognitive function. Actively designing to promote human cognitive participation and learning will go a long way in mitigating potential negative effects of GenAI use.

Finally, infrastructure for low-latency use is also important. High latency could kill potential productivity gains of leveraging chatbots, so investing in proper infrastructure is vital whether in-cloud or on-premise.

F. Cognitive Science Synthesis

The findings presented are consistent with the view of distributed cognition where cognition is not confined to the skull of an individual, but involves many external and internal artifacts—an idea proposed by Hutchins and Klausen in 1995

[21], or as Andy Clark noted, humans are “hybrid thinking systems” [6]. From this perspective, GenAI tools serve as external representational media which maintain representational state along with the human mind. This is supported by the findings presented in A. Cognitive Offloading and the Extended Mind where it is shown that cognitive misers readily offload tasks to GenAI, potentially freeing up cognitive capacity for other tasking. However, as shown in D. Metacognition and over-reliance, metacognitive laziness may occur as a result of the ease and scale of offloading, risking important human cognitive functions like problem solving and attention. In essence, the human’s activation in the distributed cognitive system can decrease to the point of near non-involvement. Metacognitive prompting provides a potential solution to this problem and also hints at another layer at which distributed cognition is at play. As GenAI chatbots ask questions, point out biases, and engage humans in the cognitive process, the system exhibits socially distributed cognition going beyond a question-answer representational machine to a rich conversational agent and thereby integrating GenAI chatbots as a part of our social system which we can use for learning and enhancing our cognitive skills.

When considering this sort of extended mind, there are interesting implications for evaluating performance of a knowledge worker. As hinted by Hernández-Orallo in “Enhancement and assessment in the AI age: An extended mind perspective,” whether we evaluate metrics at the individual mind or at cognitive system level could be paramount in how we assess the impacts of GenAI on mental processes like problem solving and attention [22]. I recommend that future research consider at what level the human hybrid thinking system is evaluated when constructing research design and evaluating metrics. Is it the cognitive process in the skull, or the cognitive process inclusive of external representations and social learning which is important? Likely the answer will be different depending on the domain of study. But it is important to bear in mind that differing answers to this question could lead to dramatically different results when assessing cognitive capacities like problem solving and attention where, for example, problem solving from the perspective of distributed cognition could be positively affected when users offload extensively to a powerful intelligent assistant, but from the perspective of the individual, negatively impacted as human deskilling and metacognitive laziness occur.

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, daily generative AI chatbot use by knowledge workers for the completion of workplace tasks can either benefit or detriment attention and problem-solving depending on user literacy, tool design, and usage style. It is how AI is used rather than if it is used that is the determinant. Compelling evidence exists that when the task fits within the “jagged frontier” of task-AI fit, the knowledge worker has task domain understanding, is metacognitively involved in the task, and has trust and confidence in the tool, attention and problem-solving capacity are positively affected in addition to gains

in productivity, learning, and efficiency. When companies, teams, and individuals thoughtfully design tools and trainings to promote these things, GenAI chatbots can be of significant benefit, extending human cognition.

V. LIMITATIONS

This review largely focused on problem solving and attention, however, broader ethical concerns around GenAI use extend beyond performance metrics. Exploring implications of cognitive offloading on overall quality of life is important to understanding how best to incorporate GenAI chatbots in the workplace.

Further, this review extrapolated results from short term studies and speculative writing to investigate concepts like metacognitive laziness and eroding skill bases. These should be explicitly studied in long-term research which can substantiate or reject these claims.

Finally, the rapid proliferation of GenAI chatbots and, more broadly, AI tools means that studies on the effects of current tools may not generalize well to future tools. It will be important that studies are replicated and theoretically validated on future GenAI tools.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Dell'Acqua *et al.*, "Navigating the jagged technological frontier: Field-experimental evidence of the effects of AI on knowledge-worker productivity and quality," *Harvard Bus. Sch. Working Paper*, no. 24-013, 2023.
- [2] M. Urban *et al.*, "ChatGPT improves creative problem-solving performance in university students: An experimental study," *Comput. Educ.*, vol. 215, Art. no. 105031, 2024.
- [3] Y. Jing *et al.*, "What factors will affect the effectiveness of using ChatGPT to solve programming problems? A quasi-experimental study," *Humanit. Soc. Sci. Commun.*, vol. 11, Art. no. 27, 2024.
- [4] M. Gerlich, "AI tools in society: Impacts on cognitive off-loading and the future of critical thinking," *Societies*, vol. 15, Art. 6, 2025.
- [5] U. León-Domínguez, "Potential cognitive risks of generative transformer-based AI chatbots on higher-order executive functions," *Front. Psychol.*, vol. 15, Art. 120018, 2024.
- [6] A. Clark, "Extending minds with generative AI," *Nat. Commun.*, vol. 16, Art. 4627, 2025.
- [7] S. R. R. Nijssen, G. Schaap, and G. P. Verheijen, "Has your smartphone replaced your brain? Construction and validation of the Extended Mind Questionnaire (XMQ)," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 13, no. 8, Art. e0202188, 2018.
- [8] S. Grinschgl, F. Papenmeier, and H. S. Meyerhoff, "Mutual interplay between cognitive off-loading and secondary task performance," *Psychon. Bull. Rev.*, vol. 30, pp. 2250–2261, 2023.
- [9] N. Barr, G. Pennycook, J. A. Stolz, and J. A. Fugelsang, "The brain in your pocket: Evidence that smartphones are used to supplant thinking," *Comput. Hum. Behav.*, vol. 48, pp. 473–480, 2015.
- [10] E. Ophir, C. Nass, and A. D. Wagner, "Cognitive control in media multitaskers," *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA*, vol. 106, no. 37, pp. 15583–15587, 2009.
- [11] M. K. Hasan, "Digital multitasking and hyperactivity: Unveiling the hidden costs to brain health," *Ann. Med. Surg.*, vol. 86, Art. 6371, 2024.
- [12] R. Suriano, A. Plebe, A. Acciai, and R. A. Fabio, "Student interaction with ChatGPT can promote complex critical thinking skills," *Learn. Instr.*, vol. 95, Art. 102011, 2025.
- [13] Y.-T. Chuang, H.-L. Chiang, and A.-P. Lin, "Insights from the Job Demands–Resources model: AI's dual impact on employees' work and life well-being," *Int. J. Inf. Manag.*, vol. 83, Art. 102887, 2025.
- [14] A. Singh, K. Taneja, Z. Guan, and A. Ghosh, "Protecting human cognition in the age of AI," *arXiv Preprint arXiv:2502.12447*, 2025.
- [15] S. Jaffe *et al.*, *Generative AI in Real-World Workplaces: The Second Microsoft Report on AI and Productivity*, Microsoft Research Tech. Rep. MSR-TR-2024-29, 2024.
- [16] Microsoft, "Reinvent productivity with Microsoft 365 Copilot," Microsoft, Redmond, WA, USA. [Online]. Available: <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/microsoft-365/copilot>. [Accessed: Jul. 5, 2025].
- [17] S. T. Fiske and S. E. Taylor, *Social Cognition: From Brains to Culture*, 4th ed. Thousand Oaks, CA, USA: SAGE, 2021, ch. 1, p. 15.
- [18] D. Kahneman, *Thinking, Fast and Slow*. New York, NY, USA: Farrar, Straus and Giroux, 2011.
- [19] J. Hollan, E. Hutchins, and D. Kirsh, "Distributed cognition: Toward a new foundation for human-computer interaction research," *ACM Trans. Comput.-Hum. Interact.*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 174–196, June 2000.
- [20] D. Kahneman, P. Slovic, and A. Tversky, Eds., *Judgment under Uncertainty: Heuristics and Biases*. Cambridge, U.K.: Cambridge Univ. Press, 1982.
- [21] E. Hutchins and T. Klausen, "Distributed cognition in an airline cockpit," in *Cognition and Communication at Work*, Y. Engeström and D. Middleton, Eds. Cambridge, U.K.: Cambridge Univ. Press, 1996, ch. 2, pp. 15–34.
- [22] J. Hernández-Orallo, "Enhancement and assessment in the AI age: An extended mind perspective," *Journal of Pacific Rim Psychology*, vol. 19, Art. no. 18344909241309376, Jan. 2025, doi: 10.1177/18344909241309376.